

Monitoring and Adapting to Changing Lake Ice Conditions

In the Arctic, lake ice conditions are vital for transportation, safety, and cultural practices. Yet, climate change is making ice seasons shorter and more unpredictable. People in Arctic regions need reliable, up-to-date lake ice information, but current data is scattered, difficult to use, or not available at all in remote areas. Many rely on informal channels like WhatsApp, which are not always accurate or accessible to all.

This integrated lake ice service empowers communities, improves safety, and bridges science with real-life decisions.

Satellite Data

**In-situ
measurements**

Local knowledge

Nearly 90% of our users say that information from Lake Ice Service affects their actions - from **planning routes** to **protecting livelihoods**.

The Lake Ice Service brings together satellite data, in-situ measurements, and local knowledge to ensure clear, accessible, and timely information on lake ice conditions, where users can also report cracks and other risks they observe on satellite images and share this with others.

To sustain and improve the Lake Ice Service, observation networks must be expanded, especially in remote Arctic areas. Strengthening collaboration with local communities and integrating lake ice information into broader Arctic observing systems will support safer and more informed decision-making.

<https://tarkka.syke.fi/map/>

ACCESS THE LAKE ICE SERVICE HERE

